

FUNCTIONAL POTENTIAL OF WHEATGRASS AND FENUGREEK IN DETOX BEVERAGE FORMULATION: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

The review aims to explore the therapeutic potential of wheatgrass and fenugreek as core ingredients in detox drink formulations. Emphasizing their antioxidant, hepatoprotective, hypoglycemic, and gut-health-enhancing properties, the study highlights their synergistic action in promoting natural detoxification. It also discusses their nutritional composition, consumer preferences, and functional beverage trends. Findings advocate their inclusion in plant-based wellness drinks and recommend further clinical trials to establish standardized usage and health efficacy.

Keywords: *Functional food, Antioxidants, Phytochemicals*

Introduction

Detox Drinks: An Overview

Toxin accumulation in the body can be caused by air pollution, chemical preservatives, food waste, the body's inherent cellular waste, and stress, resulting in sickness in any organ, joint, or tissue. The body's principal eliminatory organs include the kidneys, lungs, liver, bowels, and skin. Short fasts with water and veggies. Broths, herbs, and some fruit juices can help neutralise toxins in the bloodstream while also stimulating the liver, colon, and kidneys' cleansing activities [9].

The goal of detox water, an alternative medicine treatment, is to cleanse the body of unknown "toxins." Many bioactive substances, including flavonoids, carotenoids, and phenolic acids, are found in fruits, vegetables, and herbs. These phytochemicals scavenge free radicals to produce antioxidant effects. By submerging the plant materials in water, the phytochemicals can be released. Water infusion is the term for this technique [3].

Every other second of the day, the body goes through a natural physiological process called detoxification to get rid of waste and undesirable chemicals that could damage the body if they are present in excess or are not removed. These include endogenous toxins, which are created by the body's own metabolic processes and gut bacteria, as well as

chemicals to which we are exposed in our surroundings, such as plastics, heavy metals, food ingredients, pesticides, and pollution [12].

Detoxification is a process with several reactions and participants rather than a single response. The primary organ in charge of detoxifying xenobiotics, such as medications and harmful endogenous substances, is the liver. The detoxification process, also known as xenobiotic metabolism, is divided into three distinct phases: Phase I involves enzymatic modification, Phase II focuses on conjugation reactions, and Phase III facilitates the transport of the resulting compounds [34].

Nowadays, individuals rely on herbal products because of their benefits in maintaining a healthy and active lifestyle. Consumers place a higher value on nutritious foods; thus, food experts are working hard to incorporate plant-based ingredients into products that match these demands [33].

Origin and Taxonomy

Wheat Grass

Triticum aestivum, or common wheat, is harvested before it flowers to produce wheat grass. The origin of wheat grass is unclear, although it is grown and processed on varying scales in many nations. The majority of nations, including those in Asia and Europe, mostly consume wheat grass through juices, pills (used in therapeutic products) and as dietary enhancers in the form of powders and diverse wheatgrass-based extracts (Ogutu et al., 2017). Structurally, wheatgrass has smooth, unbranched stems that are either hollow or filled with soft tissue. Its foliage typically extends up to 1.2 meters, with narrow, flat blades measuring between 20 and 38 cm in length and about 1.3 cm in width. The seed heads, or spikes, are elongated, narrow, slightly flattened, and compressed along the dorsal surface [25].

Table 1
Taxonomy of wheat grass

Kingdom	Plantae-Plants
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta- Vascular Plants
Super division	Spermophyta (Seed producing plants)
Division	Magnoliphyta (Angiosperms)
Class	Liliopsida (Monocots)
Subclass	Commelinidae
Order	Cyperales
Family	Poaceae (Grass family)
Genus	Triticum
Species	T. aestivum

Source: (Priyanka Somkuvar et al., 2024)

Fenugreek

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum L.*) is a herbaceous annual plant that belongs to the Fabaceae family. The *Trigonella* genus comprises more than 50 different species. Its origin traces back to the Mediterranean regions of South-Eastern Europe and Western Asia, where it naturally thrives and has been cultivated for centuries. The Indian subcontinent is considered a secondary center of origin due to its wide genetic diversity and the presence of wild varieties. Notably, fenugreek ranks among the oldest crops in India. Archaeological findings, including charred fenugreek seeds discovered in Rohilla village in Punjab's Sangrur district, confirm its trade and usage during the Harappan civilization, dating back to around 2000–1700 BCE [15].

Table 2
Taxonomy of Fenugreek

Kingdom	Plantae (Plants)
Subkingdom	Tracheobionata (Vascular plants)
Superdivision	Spermatophyte (Seed plants)
Division	Magnoliophyta (Flowering plants)
Class	Magnoliopsida (Dicotyledons)
Subclass	Rosidae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	<i>Trigonella L</i>
Species	<i>Trigonella foenum- graecum L</i>

Source: (Verma et al., 2020)

Nutritional Importance and Composition

Wheat Grass

Wheatgrass offers an impressive range of nutrients, including essential minerals like iron, calcium, magnesium, selenium, chlorophyll, and carotene. It also provides proteins, carbohydrates, dietary fiber, and a spectrum of vitamins such as A, C, E, folic acid, niacin, and riboflavin. In addition to its strong antioxidant profile, which supports the management of conditions like cardiovascular disorders and diabetes. Wheatgrass contains 17 amino acids, of which eight are essential, making it a natural contributor to blood formation [11].

Wheatgrass, classified as a green vegetable, is harvested in its early growth stage before flowering occurs. It serves as a potent nutritional booster, offering approximately 860 mg of protein, 18.5 mg of chlorophyll, 15 mg of calcium, 38 mg of lysine, and 7.5 mg of vitamin C. In addition to these, it supplies a wide array of micronutrients such as B-complex vitamins and essential amino acids. From a phytochemical standpoint, wheatgrass comprises various beneficial compounds including saponins, alkaloids, complex carbohydrates, plant gums, and mucilage, all of which enhance its functional value. It is discovered that its extractive value in water is higher than its extractive value in alcohol. Because wheatgrass contains roughly 70 Per cent water-soluble chlorophyll, this is the case [26].

Table 3
Constituents of Wheatgrass (100 g)

Nutrients	Minerals	Vitamins
Calories: 21.0 Cal	Iron: 0.61 mg	Vitamin C: 3.46 mg
Water: 95 g	Magnesium: 24 mg	Vitamin A: 427 IU
Fat: 0.06 g	Phosphorous: 75.2 mg	Vitamin B1: 0.08 mg
Carbohydrates: 2.0 g	Potassium: 147 mg	Vitamin B2: 0.13 mg
Dietary fiber: <0.1 g	Zinc: 0.33 mg	Vitamin B3: 0.11 mg
Chlorophyll: 42.2 mg	Sodium: 10.3 mg	Vitamin B5: 6.0 mg
Choline: 92.4 mg	Selenium: <1 ppm	Vitamin B6: 0.2 mg
Glucose: 0.80 mg	Calcium: 24.2 mg	Vitamin B12: <1 mcg

Source: Padalia et al., 2010

Amino Acid Profile (mg)			
Alanine	69	Lysine	38
Arginine	66	Methionine	18
Aspartic acid	50	Phenylalanine	36
Cysteine	11	Proline	46
Glutamic acid	76	Serine	31
Glycine	49	Threonine	42
Histidine	18	Tryptophan	6
Isoleucine	35	Tyrosine	33
Leucine	72	valine	48

Minerals & Trace Elements mg/g			
Boron	0.0055	Chromium	0.0012
Chloride	0.49	Tin	0.0005
Manganese	0.026	Germanium	0.011
Cobalt	0.0005	Titanium	0.0005
Iodine	0.0005	Fluoride	0.0065
Molybdenum	0.0005	Copper	0.027
Silicon	0.16	Vanadium	0.0005

Source: Beniwal et al., 2022.

Fenugreek

The seeds of fenugreek feature a compact yellow-colored embryo encased within a thick, whitish, semi-translucent endosperm layer. Nutritionally, the seeds comprise approximately 23–26% protein, 6–7% fat, and about 58% carbohydrates, with nearly 25% represented by dietary fiber. Iron content is substantial, measuring 33 mg per 100 grams of dry seeds [36].

Spice moisture content ranges between 10.78 and 11.53 grams per 100 grams, signifying favorable conditions for long-term storage. The endosperm segment of the seed demonstrates a total ash value of 4.58 g/100 g—slightly higher than that of the whole seed (3.9 g/100 g) and husk (2.17 g/100 g). In terms of protein concentration, the endosperm is significantly richer (43.78 g/100 g) compared to the husk (7.9 g/100 g). Fat levels are also higher in the endosperm (6.5 g/100 g) than in the husk (1.3 g/100 g). Fiber distribution shows that fenugreek husk is particularly rich in total dietary fiber (TDF), containing 77.1 g/100 g. Of this, soluble dietary fiber (SDF) makes up 45.2 g/100 g and insoluble dietary fiber (IDF) accounts for 31.9 g/100 g. Conversely, the endosperm contains a lower fiber profile, with TDF at 34.32 g/100 g, including 20.75 g/100 g of SDF and 13.57 g/100 g of IDF [18].

Table 4
Nutritional Composition of Fenugreek

Nutrients	Amount (100 g)
Carbohydrates	58%
Proteins	23-26%
Fats	0.9%
Fibre	25%
Potassium	603 mg
Magnesium	42 mg
Calcium	75 mg
Zinc	2.4 mg
Manganese	0.9 mg
Copper	0.9 mg
Iron	25.8 mg
Vitamin C	220 mg
Beta Carotene	19 mg

Source: (Syed et al., 2020)

Therapeutic Benefits Properties of Wheat Grass

Wheatgrass is considered beneficial in the management of several health issues, including liver disorders, colon cancer, cardiovascular ailments, osteoporosis, kidney and bladder stones, and thalassemia. Its high content of antioxidants and antimicrobial compounds contributes to these effects (Beniwal et al., 2022). Additionally, it has been associated with relief from numerous chronic and lifestyle-related conditions such as asthma, thyroid imbalances, skin problems, atherosclerosis, acne, Parkinson's disease, joint discomfort, unpleasant body odour, menstrual irregularities, tuberculosis, constipation, high blood pressure, diabetes, respiratory problems, sleep disturbances, eczema, infertility, obesity, oxidative stress, and digestive bloating [8].

Wheatgrass has long been used as a cleaning and cleansing herb, but it also has therapeutic uses. Supplementing with wheatgrass reduces oxidative stress and improves protection against lipid peroxidation [29].

As the liver plays a central role in detoxification, maintaining its health is vital for overall well-being. Wheatgrass juice supports liver function not only through its rich chlorophyll content but also due to the presence of choline and essential minerals. Choline has been shown to prevent fat buildup in the liver, particularly in animals fed cholesterol-rich diets. It facilitates the breakdown of glycerol and cholesterol esters, beginning with the glycerides and subsequently impacting cholesterol compounds. Within the body, choline is metabolized into an active form that is stored in liver cells, where it aids in the oxidation of fatty acids and the synthesis of tissue lecithins. This lipotropic activity enhances the formation of lipoproteins, which help transport fatty acids through the bloodstream and reduce fat accumulation in liver [23].

The structure of the chlorophyll molecule closely resembles that of heme, the pigment that binds with proteins to form hemoglobin. Chlorophyll also contains beneficial enzymes and the copper-based protein superoxide dismutase, which is found in mature red blood cells. This enzyme plays a role in slowing aging by neutralizing harmful superoxide radicals into less reactive forms within the body.

Chlorophyll as green blood: The structure of their porphyrin heads can be used to illustrate the similarity between hemoglobin and chlorophyll. The two compounds' tetra pyrrole ring structures are remarkably similar; the only distinction between them is the type of central metal atoms found in iron (Fe) in hemoglobin and magnesium (Mg) in chlorophyll. Additionally, The pH level of wheatgrass juice is approximately 7.4, which is comparable to

blood and aids in rapid blood absorption. As a result, this fluid is frequently called "**Green Blood.**" Thus, wheat grass juice aids in blood formation and has several medicinal uses, including: raising red blood cell counts; acting as a blood builder in thalassemia major; treating haemolytic anaemia with adjuvant therapy; and providing supportive care for cancer patients nearing the final stage of their illness. The treatment of inflammatory bowel illness. It enhances metabolic and digestive processes [19].

Wheatgrass juice helps to cure complications with elevated blood uric acid include bodily edema, digestive issues, insomnia, and more. Wheat grass juice is a great way to treat toothaches and prevent tooth decay. Chewing wheat grass can have positive effects. This section covers the issues of kidney inflammation, bladder inflammation, and stone formation. Regular consumption of wheat grass juice improves outcomes and speeds up recovery. The two illnesses that this therapy can treat rather easily are dysmenorrhea and sexual debility. Consuming wheatgrass juice and applying its tender parts topically has been reported to offer therapeutic relief for certain intimate health conditions [17].

Blood sugar issues are resolved with chlorophyll. It may be possible to effectively manage diabetes mellitus by include wheat grass in a diabetic diet (Kothari et al., 2011). A significant contributor to modern health problems is the reduced intake of dietary fiber. As a natural source of fiber, wheatgrass powder supplementation has shown promising effects in managing diabetes and helping to regulate blood glucose levels. The active chlorophyll in spray-dried wheatgrass juice acts as a pharmacological anti-diabetic drug [4].

It is a potent source of minerals such as iron, calcium, and magnesium. The natural enzymes it contains enhance its digestibility, making it more readily absorbed compared to synthetic vitamin and mineral supplements. Improved digestion through wheatgrass intake may lead to increased absorption of essential nutrients. Additionally, its natural antibiotic properties have been linked to the prevention of oral health concerns, including tooth decay, gum infections, cold sores, yeast overgrowth, mouth ulcers, and halitosis. Wheatgrass also promotes the formation of red blood cells, which may accelerate the healing process following dental treatments [28].

Uses of Vitamins and Minerals

Vitamin A: It gives the outside skin a glow and improves its luster while preventing sickness.

Vitamin B: It aids in digestion. It helps treat anorexia, mental distress, sleeplessness, premature aging, and digestive issues.

Vitamin C: It helps prevent diseases like scurvy and aids in the recovery from illnesses like the common cold. It is essential for maintaining bones and having healthy gums and teeth [13].

Vitamin E: It allows blood to circulate freely by widening capillaries. Abortion, diabetes, cancer, heart disease, dysmenorrhea, and other conditions are prevented by it. In addition to being a reproductive and antioxidant vitamin, it also protects the heart.

Vitamin B and Vitamin K: It contains vitamin B-17, also known as amygdalin, which has been explored in some studies for its potential role in cancer prevention. Alongside its vitamin content, wheatgrass supplies 92 essential minerals and 17 amino acids that are important for various physiological functions. Its rich nutrient profile is also believed to support the repair of damaged lung cells and may offer protective effects against cancer [10].

Iron: It helps with excessive perspiration, pale skin, sleeplessness, and lethargy during pregnancy. Iron salts found in wheatgrass have no negative consequences, however inorganic iron frequently causes constipation.

Calcium: The primary inducer of vital activity is calcium. It gives older people more vigour, strengthens bones, and returns the body to an alkaline state for children. It is useful in the treatment of conditions including varicose veins, slow movements, coldness, body distension, and haemorrhage.

Potassium: Beneficial for depression, suicidal thoughts, palpitations, fatigue, dementia, hypertension, and youthful radiance and luster. A balanced body weight and a smooth mineral balance are maintained by potassium, which some nutritionists refer to as the youth mineral.

Zinc: It plays a vital role in supporting prostate health and contributes to hair nourishment.

Sodium: It is essential for maintaining extracellular fluid volume, regulating the body's acid-base balance, and ensuring proper hydration.

Magnesium: It is crucial for healthy muscle activity and digestive health, as it supports regular elimination processes [17].

Health Benefits of Wheatgrass

Wheatgrass has demonstrated potential health benefits in managing a variety of conditions, such as anemia, diabetes, cancer, eczema, constipation, kidney inflammation, and common respiratory illnesses like colds. Including wheatgrass as part of a regular diet may help optimize its therapeutic effects. It is known to combat fatigue, enhance sleep quality, and improve physical stamina. Additionally, wheatgrass may aid in the natural regulation of blood pressure and blood sugar, support healthy weight management, and promote effective digestion and waste elimination. It contributes to the well-being of the skin, teeth, eyes, muscles, and joints, while also supporting cardiovascular, respiratory, and reproductive functions. Furthermore, it is credited with accelerating the healing of ulcers and skin lesions, enhancing mental clarity, reducing signs of cellular aging, and alleviating symptoms related to arthritis and muscle cramps [28].

Properties of Fenugreek

Fenugreek's therapeutic benefits are function in reducing insulin resistance, VLDL (Very Low Density Lipoprotein) overproduction, and rheumatoid arthritis increased insulin sensitivity due to glucose transporter overexpression. *Trigonella* possesses antibacterial, antifungal, and anticancer qualities and protects against gallstones, gastric ulcers, neurological conditions, pulmonary fibrosis, obesity, and asthma [31].

One herb that has long been used in medicine as an appetiser and laxative is fenugreek. Numerous experts have examined this herb's various qualities as well as how it affects fertility. The seeds of fenugreek have oestrogenic properties. Additionally, it was discovered that the seeds raised the level of prolactin in the blood. According to reports, fenugreek has antioxidant, immunomodulatory, hypoglycaemic, and hypercholesterolemic properties. Fenugreek seeds are widely utilized in traditional Chinese medicine due to their diverse therapeutic properties, including hypolipidemic, anti-obesity, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antidiabetic, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antifungal effects. Additionally, it demonstrated a favourable impact on the treatment of mouth ulcers, high blood pressure, gastrointestinal irritation, diuretics, and arthritis pain. For vegans, it can be regarded as dietary protein that is unavailable in diets high in fish and animals [14].

Fenugreek leaves and seeds were recommended due to their haematinic properties. According to reports, the fenugreek seeds have a high iron level, and their germination enhances their vitamin A, B, and C content. They offer nutritional and restorative qualities, are high in proteins that contain vital amino acids, ascorbate, and folate, and have been shown

to increase blood haemoglobin. Additionally, fenugreek has been used to control hyperthyroidism and shield the liver from ethanol- and aluminium chloride-induced hepatotoxicity. It was discovered to be an effective treatment for inflammatory and allergic disorders. The seeds of fenugreek have long been utilised as an herbal remedy for nutritional and metabolic disorders. According to certain research, taking supplements containing fenugreek seed extract may help lower body and fat tissue weight. It may reduce weight by flushing out carbs from the body before they enter the bloodstream, which is the likely method by which it lowers body weight and adipose tissue weight [1].

Pharmaceutical Uses of Fenugreek

Table 5
Pharmaceutical Uses of Fenugreek

Components Used	Beneficial Uses
Seeds	Hypocholesterolemic effects
	Prevents constipation
	For healthy heart
	Lactation aid
	Immunomodulatory effects
	Induces reproduction and growth hormones
	Digestive effects
Leaves and Seeds	Hypoglycemic effects
	Used as an antioxidant
	Gastro-and hepatoprotective
	Anticancer agents
	Wounds and sore muscles treatment
	Decreases blood pressure

Source: (Naeem et al., 2021)

Fenugreek has been traditionally used to manage various ailments, including colic, flatulence, diarrhoea, indigestion accompanied by poor appetite, chronic cough, edema, rickets, gout, diabetes, and the enlargement of the liver and spleen. It is also valued for its ability to help reduce body odour and bad. Consuming fenugreek seeds on a regular basis is thought to lower blood levels of triglycerides, glucose, and total cholesterol. Because fenugreek is believed to have galactagogue qualities, Indian women eat the seeds because they can encourage lactation. Diosgenin (0.40–1.26%), a precursor to sex hormones used as a stimulant and contraceptive, is a significant component of fenugreek seeds. Fenugreek also treats baldness and helps fight dandruff [15].

India is among the leading global producers of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum L.*), with an annual output ranging between 45,000 and 55,000 tonnes. Fenugreek has been traditionally employed for a wide array of therapeutic uses, including the treatment of bronchitis, asthma, and arthritis; supporting digestive health; enhancing libido and male reproductive strength; and reducing inflammation. It is also used to manage skin conditions such as wounds, rashes, and boils, as well as to relieve sore throats and acid reflux. Additionally, fenugreek is believed to support hormonal balance, aid in reproductive health, induce labor, assist in breast tissue development, reduce menstrual discomfort, and help regulate blood glucose [22].

Health Benefits of Fenugreek

In India and China, fenugreek has long been used in traditional medicine. It can be used to treat edema and weakness in the legs, to promote appetite and lactation, and to treat fever, baldness, and indigestion. Some people have applied it topically to treat cellulitis, wounds, and myalgia. Improving increased blood glucose and lipid levels linked to long-term illnesses like diabetes and obesity is one possible advantage of fenugreek. According to human research, fenugreek may help diabetics manage their elevated blood sugar and cholesterol levels by acting as an adjuvant [30].

Drying Methods

Drying is one of the oldest methods used to preserve food and extend its shelf life. Also referred to as dehydration, it involves a combined process of heat and mass transfer that eliminates moisture from solid or liquid food materials, resulting in a final product with significantly reduced water content [6].

The rate of drying is affected by both external and internal variables. External influences include solar radiation, air temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity, while internal factors encompass the crop's initial moisture content, type, absorptive capacity, and the mass of the product per unit of exposed surface area [27].

Cabinet Drying

Cabinet dryers are ideal for drying products due to their ability to maintain optimal temperature and airflow compared to other dryers. Shorter drying time and reduced risk of microbiological deterioration lead to higher production rates and higher product quality [38].

Shade Drying

Shade drying is a UV-free technique that requires ambient air, humidity, and ventilation in a shaded area away from direct sunlight. This drying method is also known by various terms, including room drying, indoor dehydration, shadow drying, and sheltered air-drying. It is generally recommended in areas with cloudy conditions, lower humidity, or higher levels of air pollution. Dehydrating leaves in the shade maximises colour and flavour retention [5].

Consumer Preferences on Herbal Products

Consumer preferences for herbal products and plant-based drinks are driven by health consciousness, perceived safety, and cultural influences. Many individuals prefer herbal products for their natural remedies and therapeutic benefits, particularly in cultures like Indonesia that traditionally accept herbal medicine. Likewise, health benefits significantly boost the popularity of plant-based drinks, with consumers seeking organic and additive-free options. Taste, variety, and convenience of ready-to-drink products also play important roles in shaping these preferences, reflecting a broader trend towards health, safety, and sustainability [37].

Herbal items are more appealing to health-conscious people because consumers identify them with natural components and few negative consequences. According to a 2015 study in Bhopal, India, customers frequently used herbal products on a regular basis, but brand loyalty was still low because of the items limited exposure and erratic availability. The study also emphasized that faith in herbal items was strongly driven by recommendations from doctors, family members, and mass media, which greatly shaped consumer decisions. The importance of clear labelling, safety assurance, and effective health communication in promoting informed consumer choices is further highlighted by the respondents' strong desire for more trustworthy information about usage, benefits, and potential side effects [2].

Herbal products' natural therapeutic qualities and long history of usage in medicine continue to attract significant consumer acceptance. Effectiveness was found to be the most significant determinant of customer preference, demonstrating that people primarily select herbal products for their established health advantages. In comparison to chemical-based medications, consumers think herbal solutions are safer and more effective for long-term use. Many people favored herbal remedies that were both affordable and helpful, thus

affordability was also crucial. These results show how popular herbal products are becoming in everyday life, particularly when they are promoted with natural components, obvious health benefits, and cultural familiarity [20].

Consumer preference for herbal and plant-based drinks is steadily increasing due to their health benefits, natural ingredients, and cultural acceptance. These beverages are seen as safer and more sustainable alternatives to synthetic products. Factors like taste, affordability, and availability also influence consumer choices. Brands that offer transparency and convenience gain more trust. Overall, the demand for herbal and plant-based drinks reflects a shift towards healthier lifestyles.

Functional Properties of Detox Mix

Functional beverages are designed either to support overall health and physical well-being or to reduce the risk of disease onset. Diets rich in fruits, vegetables, dairy products, and herbal ingredients have been strongly associated with a reduced incidence of chronic conditions such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), which are among the leading causes of mortality in developed countries. In addition to meeting basic nutritional needs, functional foods contain bioactive compounds that may provide physiological benefits and are recommended as part of a regular diet to promote health and decrease disease risk [32].

A recent trend in dieting is the use of detox or cleaning foods. It turned oxidative. A few of these herbs claim quick weight loss. People today rely on the idea of herbal goods because of their advantages in maintaining a busy and healthy lifestyle. Food specialists are working hard to include plant-based items in products that satisfy consumers' growing need for nutrient-dense diets [33].

Conclusion

Wheatgrass and fenugreek demonstrate significant potential as functional ingredients in detox beverages due to their rich nutritional and bioactive profiles. Their antioxidative, hepatoprotective, and digestive benefits make them ideal for health-conscious consumers. While their traditional use is well-supported, scientific validation through human trials and dose standardization is essential. This comprehensive review supports incorporating these botanicals into commercial detox formulations for sustainable and natural health promotion.

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